

REEEMpathways

Stakeholder Interaction Portal (D7.1) and
Pathways Diagnostics Tool (D7.2)

About this report

This report is a brief description of REEEM pathways, the open source tool for stakeholder engagement and pathway diagnostics in the EU Horizon 2020 project REEEM (<http://www.reeem.org/>). It constitutes the formal deliverables D7.1 and D7.2 of the project.

Authors

Olavur Ellefsen (TOKNI), Marita Foldbo Holm (TOKNI), Bo Lærke Hansen (TOKNI), Helena Egholm (TOKNI), and Eyðbjörg Leo (TOKNI).

REEEM partners

Universität Stuttgart

TOKNI

About REEEM

REEEM aims to gain a clear and comprehensive understanding of the system-wide implications of energy strategies in support of transitions to a competitive low-carbon EU energy society. This project is developed to address four main objectives: (1) to develop an integrated assessment framework (2) to define pathways towards a low-carbon society and assess their potential implications (3) to bridge the science-policy gap through a clear communication using decision support tools and (4) to ensure transparency in the process.

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Summary

The REEEMpathways tool is an article-based open access online tool to visualise the results and key messages of the project in order to further enable stakeholder interaction. The tool is populated by data stored in the REEEM Pathways Database and provides public access to modelling insights, input data, and pathway assumptions from the project.

The user interface is designed with an emphasis on organising and visualising model data. A number of developed features enhance usability and accessibility. The tool allows REEEM partners to publish and update their own articles providing multiple types of static and dynamic charts to visualise their own key messages and the data behind it.

Following the concept of the REEEM project, this enables policy makers and stakeholders to explore and compare possible decarbonization pathways and hopefully this can assist in understanding the effects of and requirements for energy system changes.

The tool has been integrated with social media, enabling the public to discuss the results and key messages with REEEM partners and allowing other modellers to contribute with their knowledge.

All partners within the REEEM project have contributed to the tool by providing feedback throughout the development process. REEEMpathways has been updated throughout the project.

REEEMpathways is a part of REEEM's Stakeholder Engagement and Dissemination work package which aims at disseminating the insights gained from the project, and to get feedback from stakeholders to improve the models and other material being developed in the project.

The tool is publicly available at <https://reeempathways.org>

The source code is available at <https://github.com/ReeemProject/reeempathways>

Combination of two deliverables

Originally, the intent was to create two separate tools, a Stakeholder Interaction Portal and a Pathways Diagnostics Tool. In the grant agreement, these are listed as two separate deliverables, D7.1 and D7.2, respectively.

However, as the project progressed, it became apparent that it was a better idea to integrate the two tools into one. The main reason was that the data available in the "pathways diagnostic tool" is the best foundation for the engaging with stakeholders in the "stakeholder interaction portal", and any distinction between the two would be artificial.

After consulting with the project officer, the two deliverables were also merged. Therefore, this report comprises both deliverables.